

Research Article

"G-D's Physics" Turning Point: An Urgent Call for Astronomers' Direct Empirical Validation of The Jewish Rosh-Hashanah UNCIARE Critical Prediction!

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Note: Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm based on a "time-sensitive" measurement of a predicted increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days' time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics; Dr. Bentovish (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentovish@gmail.com

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) & Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) following a "Paradigmatic Crisis" of the Old Paradigm signified by an apparent GRT-QM "theoretical inconsistency" and its inability to explain the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion (assumed to be "caused" by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts comprising up to 95% of the mass and energy in the universe but which cannot be detected for the past two full decades!?) In contrast, a new "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been discovered pointing at the existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50}$ sec' (!) Two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm are empirically validated thereby establishing the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm as the New (satisfactory) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century! An urgent call is made to all Astronomers to collaborate with Dr. Bentovish (drbentwich@gmail.com) by validating "G-D's Physics" eve more direct "Critical Prediction" regarding an increase in the universe's expansion rate – beginning in the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah's (JRH's) two-days' (Sep. 16th-17th, 2023 and onwards) due to "G-D's Physics" postulated "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF)!

Introduction

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics has reached a "historic point" akin only to the acceptance of Einstein's General Relativity Theory (GRT) as the New 20th Century Scientific Paradigm – following Eddington's unequivocal empirical validation of Einstein's "double-valued" Mercury's perihelion curvature around the Sun (during the famous 1919 Solar Eclipse)! This is because based on Thomas Kuhn's famous analysis of the Structure of Scientific Revolutions (1962), the manner in which Science is willing to embrace any new Scientific Paradigm instead of the Old "Standard Paradigm" is contingent upon the satisfaction of these stringent scientific conditions:

- There appears to exist a clear "Paradigmatic-Crisis" in the foundation of the Old "Standard Paradigm", e.g., as signified by the existence of certain "theoretical-inconsistencies" between the "pillars" of the Old "Standard Paradigm", and there exist certain (key) "unexplained empirical phenomenon" that cannot be explained by this Old "Standard Paradigm".
- The New (prospective) Scientific Paradigm (NSP) is shown capable of resolving those apparent "theoretical-inconsistencies" found in the foundations of the Old Paradigm, and also offers an alternative (satisfactory) explanation for the (key) "unexplained empirical phenomenon"!

c) The NSP is shown to be capable of replicating most of the laws and phenomena explained by the Old Standard Paradigm.

d) This NSP identifies- and empirically validates- at least one (unique) "Critical Prediction" of this NSP as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old Standard Paradigm!

Indeed, all of these stringent scientific criteria were met in the case of Einstein's discovery and Eddington's empirical validation of GRT's ("NSP") unique "Critical Prediction" of Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion pathway around the Sun (during the 1919 Solar Eclipse)! Similarly, it is suggested that the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) satisfies all of these stringent scientific conditions:

- There seems to exist a basic "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM stemming from GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) imposed upon the transmission of any signal across space and time, as opposed to QM's empirically validated "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon in which a measurement of (one of two: mass/time or energy/mass) "complementary" physical features in one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects the other complimentary particle's physical features, e.g., thereby seemingly "violating" GRT's strict SLB!? Additionally, a key phenomenon

relating to the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion cannot be explained by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm – since it assumes that this accelerated expansion of the universe is "caused" by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" (DM/DE) concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but yet cannot be verified experimentally (even after two full decades of intensive experimentations attempting to "detect" those purely hypothetical concept)?!

B) In contrast, a newly discovered "G-D's Physics" (previously termed: the "Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) Scientific Paradigm was shown capable of resolving this apparent GRT-QM "theoretical inconsistency" based on its discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{-50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ " thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"; As previously delineated this allows the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm to resolve the apparent GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency based on its recognition of this singular UCP's "Single Spatial Temporal" (SST) vs. "Multiple Spatial-Temporal" (MST) and (broadest) "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" (EST) computations!

According to the New G-D'S PHYSICS's computational analysis, this "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" for the transmission of any "signal" (or even "information") across "space" and "time" – which seems to be "contradicted" by QM's "Quantum Entanglement Phenomenon", indicating that the measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects the "complimentary" ("space/energy" or "mass/time") measurement of the other "entangled particle"?! But, according to the new CUT's Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation- and "resolution"- of this apparent "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from the UCP's singular (higher-ordered simultaneous) computation of all "Single Spatial-Temporal" computation ("SST"): "particle" of relativistic "object" (e.g., relating to only "one" spatial-temporal point, at any given moment), "Multi Spatial-Temporal" computation (MST): "wave" (e.g., relating to at least "two" points being measured at any point in time) or "Exhaustive Spatial Temporal" (EST) computation (e.g., relating to all "exhaustive" spatial pixels comprising an entire "Universal Frame", UF), across a series of UF's frames (Figure 3);

FIGURE 3: UCP'S "SST", "MST" & "EST" COMPUTATIONS

UCP's Computations	SST	MST
Num. "ST" Points	1	2+

C) The New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) of "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" was also shown capable of "replicating" all previous Relativistic & Quantum phenomena and laws (as outlined previously).

D) Most significantly, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has identified at least two unique "Critical Predictions" which can differentiate "G-D's Physics" NSP from the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm – which if validated empirically must lead the Scientific Community to accept "G-D's Physics" NSP as "more valid" than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, thereby accepting "G-D's Physics" as the New (satisfactory) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stem-

ming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(n)\}] = O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i..n)\}) / h * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i..n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by Pohl et al. (2010) :

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

Pohl et al.[54-56] set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(n)\}] = O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i..n)\}) / h * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed

to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force"⁴⁹, interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction [53,57], higher dimension gravity⁴⁸, a new boson [52], and the quasi-free hypothesis π^+ [51], and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion⁵⁸⁻⁶¹! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational

Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Discussion

Based on the above results indicating that "G-D's Physics" (CUFT) two unique "Critical Predictions" of the UNCIARE accelerated increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, and the Proton-Radius Puzzle associated findings are found to be more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's; therefore, we must accept this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm as more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of 20th century's Theoretical Physics)! But, before we outline the far-reaching theoretical ramifications of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, it is important to point out another (direct) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in continuation to the already validated UNCIARE unique Critical Prediction: As mentioned above, the UNCIARE Critical Prediction's empirical validation denotes that the universe's rate of expansion has increased from its early stage "Background Radiation" Cosmological measures to the current Astronomical indices of its contemporary rate of expansion! As noted, this result confirms "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE Critical Prediction wherein the universe's accelerated rate of expansion increases over time – in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's assumption wherein the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" is assumed to "cause" a "constant-rate" expansion of the universe (e.g., despite the abovementioned principle negation of the Old "Material-Causal" SRCS/SRNCs "flawed" computational structure which was negated by "G-D's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle", CDP)! Hence, the increase in the universe's rate of expansion over time has already been validated (as the unique UNCIARE Critical Prediction of "G-D's Physics") – but a more specific (direct) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm can be tested based on a specific "time-sensitive" measurement of the universe's increase in its expansion rate during the two-days' special time-interval of the "Jewish Rosh-Hashanah" (JRH, New Year) due this year on September 16th & 17th (2023) and onwards – relative to the universe's rate of expansion prior to Sep. 16th & 17th (expected to be lower than the rate of expansion from Sep. 16th & 17th)! As noted earlier, this (specific) unique Critical Prediction of "G-D's Physics" regarding the UNCIARE-JRH's increase in the universe's rate of expansion, e.g., during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" is hypothesized to be due to "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis", wherein it is assumed that whenever there is a Collective Human Consciousness Focus, e.g., in this case of Millions of Jews all (collectively) focusing on this singular UCP, then this brings about a "Non-Continuous Increase in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (JRH-UNCIARE Critical Prediction)!

Therefore, I am calling all Astronomers and Cosmologists (in the world) to carry out this important further direct empirical validation of the JRH-UNCIARE Critical Prediction – which if validated, will provide yet another (direct) support for "G-D's Physics" New 21st Century Scientific Paradigm!

The theoretical ramifications of the acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New Physics Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century are quite far-reaching: first, the New "G-D's Physics" is an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm which negates the very possibility of the existence of any "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different UF's frame/s: This is because according to the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s, negates the possibility of the existence of any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels for any given UF frame; and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! As delineated previously this New "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm challenges and negates GRT's "Big-Bang" Model, ne-

gates the existence of "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" (as superfluous, i.e., "non-existent") as well as more generally the SRCS/SRNCS basic Computational Structure underlying the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., including its GRT's assumption wherein it is the direct physical interaction between certain "massive objects" and "Space-Time" which "causes" the "curvature of Space-Time" (and conversely determines or "causes" the "travelling-pathways" of those "massive" and other "less-massive" objects); and likewise negates QM's equivalent "Material-Causal" basic assumption, wherein it is assumed that it is the direct "material-causal" physical interaction between a given subatomic "probe" and a corresponding subatomic "target" that "causes" the "collapse" of the assumed target's "probability wave-function"!

Instead, a major discovery made by this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm is the complete unification – not only between GRT & QM, but also between the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (as well as between the four basic Forces!) within a newly discovered "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF), which explicates the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! This major UCF discovery stems from "G-D's Physics" novel computation of these four basic physical features as underlie by the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency": According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm the UCP computes for each given (relativistic or subatomic) object – its degree of "Consistency" (e.g., "consistent" or "inconsistent") relative to two possible "Framework" levels, i.e., relative to the entire "frame" or relative to the "object" itself (i.e., internal composition), which gives rise to those four basic physical features; That is, when the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" measures of any given object this yields the two corresponding physical features of "space" and "energy", whereas when the UCP computes the two "Object" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" measures this produces the two corresponding physical features of "mass" and "time"! Based on these new (and exciting) UCP's computational definitions of these four basic physical features (given below) the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm was able to integrate them as secondary computational features of the same singular higher-ordered UCP, thereby giving rise to this profound novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF)!

THE "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF):

$$\left. \begin{matrix} c^2 \\ - \\ h \end{matrix} \right\} \text{UF's } \{n \dots n \dots n\} [Px]_{\{a \dots z\}} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

Note: which is accompanied by "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) computational (previous) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" as representing "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") computational properties of the UCP's simultaneous and integrated computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels:

$$S: (f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] + \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) \leq f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i \dots n)]$$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i...n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure!

Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

$$E: (f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(i)] - \dots f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$$

such that:

$$f_{\{x,y,z\}}[UF(n) > f_{\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\}} [UF's(i \dots n)]$$

wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's.

In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

$$M: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] = O(i \dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i \dots n) \leq n * h \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

$$T: \sum [O_{i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}} [UF(n)] \neq O(i \dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\}) \{UF(i \dots n)\} / c * n \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

such that:

$$T: [O_{i\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i)] - O_{n\{x,y,z\}}UF's(i \dots n) \leq c * h \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in

which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light.

Significantly, it has been previously shown that this novel UCF possesses two equivalent "Relativistic Format" and "Quantum Format" which indicate that it embeds (within it) "special-cases" of well-known physical laws and characteristics of GRT such as the "Energy-Mass Equivalence" ($E = Mc^2$) and QM's "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" "complimentary pairs"; thereby pointing at "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's complete unification- embedding- and indeed transcending- of GRT & QM! However, since one of the key Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the whole universe including all of these exhaustive spatial pixels – "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames; therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm has been characterized as an "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! This is because due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and its complete "dissolution" "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames (e.g., back into the UCP's singular existence), there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s!

In fact, due to the only "transient" and "phenomenal" existence of any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, e.g., which exists only "during" the UCP's production of every consecutive UF's frame/s, but "ceases to exist" and "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frames, two additional profound Theoretical Postulates of "G-D's Physics" New Paradigm, termed: the "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" postulate: a) That the only "computationally-invariant" principle in the universe which exists both "during" the UCP's successive computation of each subsequent UF's frame/s, and solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) is this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP); as opposed to the only "transient-phenomenal" appearance of the entire physical universe – regarded as "computationally-variant", e.g., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely computed or produced by this singular UCP) but "dissolving" back into the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s; b) Therefore, there only exists one singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists uniformly, continuously and constantly – both "during" its manifestation as the physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), and also exists singularly "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe)!

Viewed from this new (higher, more exhaustive) perspective of this New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, a series of additional (profound) associated Theoretical Postulates have been discovered, including: c) The "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Postulate: hypothesizing that since there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s, the only manner in which this series of UF's frames (comprising the entire physical universe) could "evolve" is based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's "pre-planning" of the entire evolution- (or manifestation-) of the whole universe from "inanimate matter" through "animate": "plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards", i.e., based on the UCP's "pre-planning" of the whole evolution of all "inanimate" and "animate" forms leading up to this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! A Metaphor regarding "King Solomon's" build-up of the Divine Temple was utilized to explain this "Reversed-Time

Geulah Goal" Postulate: that is, in the same way that King Solomon must have received a completed "Perfected Blue-Print Plan" of the "Ultimate Completed Temple State" (e.g., and all of the necessary "steps" required to reach this "Ultimate Completed Temple State" – prior to his various builders starting to construct this immaculate Divine Temple, so it is postulated that the UCP/UCR must have "pre-planned" the whole evolution of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter", "animate": plants, animals and human-beings from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" – through the entire evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, ultimately leading to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", i.e., in which Science and the whole of Humanity will recognize the singular existence of this higher-ordered UCR, alongside the recognition of its basic characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" etc. (previously delineated).

A Brief Summary of "G-D's Physics" additional Theoretical Postulates is outlined (in order to provide an exhaustive summary of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm):

d) The UCP's Three Computational Dimensions:

Indeed, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers a new (and exciting) theoretical explanation for the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on two out of its three hypothesized "Computational Dimensions", e.g., "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent"); According to "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, the UCP simultaneously computes for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe these four basic physical features based on particular computational combinations, e.g., an "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computation derives the two (corresponding) physical features of "mass" and "time", whereas the UCP's computation of any given object's "Frame" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" values yields its "space" and "energy" characteristics!

e) The Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) "Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions":

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה"):

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of

"All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah" State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!? Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת).

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past"- "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blue-Print", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/דעת)

signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Chessed"/חסד):

This "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah" may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Devorah"/דבורה):

Denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the un

derlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/"Tiferet"):

The sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human -being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th, 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת" Tiferet which translates as "Glorification" because it

signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification- or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it is represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah symbol of "נצח" Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva"("תשובה")/"הוד"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva/ "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person choses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah term of "יסוד"/"Yessod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are

necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yessod"-Foundation Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and "power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר"/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כתר"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown"))"; This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec') for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

Negation of the "Big-Bang Model" & "Einstein's Equations' Material-Causal Assumption"!

Indeed, once we begin realizing that the entire physical universe exists only as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) (e.g., since it only exists "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s as solely computed by this singular UCR but "dissolves" back into the UCR's singularity "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s); and that (in fact) there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) relativistic or quantum (subatomic) exhaustive spatial pixels (found within the same-or different- UF's frame/s); we have to revise some

of the basic "material-causal" assumptions standing as the very "basis" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM!

Thus, for instance, the basic "Big-Bang" Model of GRT, which assumes that the entire physical universe was "caused" or "created" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event that created all of the suns, galaxies, "matter" and "energy" ("space" and "time") of the entire physical universe – was shown to be questioned and (in fact) negated by the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This is simply because if (indeed) this singular (higher-ordered) UCR simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., at the "unfathomable" rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!), and "dissolves" back into the UCR singularity "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, then there could not have been any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the first- second-... or "trillionth" UF's frame/s – which implies that the "Big-Bang" nuclear event could not have occurred, i.e., at least as "causing" the creation of all the suns, galaxies, "matter" and "energy" etc. in the universe! The only thing that could have happened is the UCR's consecutive computation of a series of UF's frames that evolved- and is (in fact) still evolving the entire physical universe (and every exhaustive spatial pixel/s comprising it) – e.g., from "inanimate" matter through "animate": "plants", "animals" and "human-beings" towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the universe, in which Science and Humanity will recognize the singularity of this UCR, alongside its "intrinsic sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

In order to better grasp this new "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm a "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" has been illustrated: depicting an imaginary "film-scenario", in which a "mercury-ball" is shown to impact a "glass-jar" (filled with water) which seems to "cause" the breakage of this "glass-jar" (and consequent "spillage of water")... But (in fact), when we "slow-down" (and even "halt") the progression of this "Cinematic-Film Metaphor", and closely examine each of these consecutive "film-frames" (separately), we can clearly discern that at each (consecutive) film-frame, all of its exhaustive spatial pixels are being depicted "simultaneously" – so that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal physical interaction" between any two (or more) spatial pixels comprising each of these (consecutive) film-frames! We also realize that there cannot exist any such "material-causal physical interaction" between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two consecutive film-frames (e.g., or in fact any two film-frames)! This is simply due to the fact that "in-between" any two such film-frames transpires a "pure-light" (of the "projector") so that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "physical interaction" between any of the (exhaustive) spatial pixels comprising one "film-frame" and any other subsequent "film-frame"! Therefore, we realize that despite the "appearance" of a "material-causal" physical interaction between the "mercury ball" and its apparent "impact" upon the "glass-jar" – which seemed to "cause" the "breakage" of this "glass-jar" (and "spillage" of water); the only thing that really "exists" is the arrangement of this series of "film-frames" depicting an (ever-closer) "proximity" of the "mercury ball" and "glass-jar" until their "conjoining" (e.g., being presented as "touching" each other) which then leads to the presentation of a broken "glass-jar" and "spillage of water"... Hence, we must realize that despite the appearance of a direct "material-causal" physical interaction between the "mercury-ball" and ("water-filled") "glass-jar" (which seems to "cause" the "breakage" of this "glass-jar" - and "spillage" of "water") – in reality, there is only an "arrangement" of this series of "film-frames" in a manner which gives us the "impression" (or "perception") of such a "material-causal" relationship between the "mercury-ball" and its "breakage" of the "glass-jar"...

Indeed, based on this (simple yet profound) "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" we can clearly understand that in the same manner that there cannot exist

any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in (any) two film-frames (e.g., due to the “simultaneous” presentation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given “film-frame” and the complete “dissolution” of all the exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given “film-frame/s” into the “pure-light” separating between any two such consecutive “film-frames”); there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (“consecutive” or even “non-consecutive”) “universal Frames” (comprising the entire physical universe at any given “minimal time-point”)! Therefore, the “material-causal” assumption underlying the “Big-Bang” Model (emanating from Einstein’s GRT) is strictly negated based on this New Twenty-First Century’s “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm! This is (once again) simply because this “Big-Bang Model” precisely assumes such “material-causal” (direct) physical interactions between an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event and its “causing” (or “creation”) of all the “suns”, “galaxies”, “matter” and “energy” (“space” and “time”) in the physical universe – which is strictly negated by “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any (consecutive) UF’s (and the complete “dissolution” of all of these exhaustive spatial pixels into the singularity of the “Universal Computational Reality”, “UCR” “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s!)

A Geulah-Driven Space-Time Evolution of the Universe!

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the “Ultimate Goal” of the entire physical universe’s development is given through “G-D’s Physics” newly discovered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another “Solomon’s Temple Blueprint Plan” Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has “preplanned” the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the “Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal”, in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”!

According to this “Solomon’s Temple Blueprint Plan” Metaphor, King Solomon had to “preplan” the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its “Completed-Perfected-Final” stage – “backwards” towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this “Blueprint Plan” will lead

up to this “Completed-Perfected-Final” state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon’s builders begin “constructing” this Immaculate Temple – without such a “perfected Blueprint Plan”, i.e., just by “experimenting” with different stones with no “preplanned Blueprint Plan” for its orderly completion?!) Equivalently, “G-D’s Physics” New (Twenty-First Century’s) “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has “preplanned” a “Blueprint Plan” – from the “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State” “backwards” towards the initial stages of “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the “Perfected Geulah State” of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any “material-causal” physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive UF’s frame/s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be “caused” by any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between certain “massive” objects and their (assumed) “curvature” of “Space-Time” (or the corresponding determination of the “travelling pathways” of these “massive” or other “less-massive” objects as “caused” by this assumed “curved Space-Time” fabric), as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe is being continuously “created”, “dissolved”, “re-created” and “evolved” so many “trillions” of time each second –by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned “Blueprint Plan” of advancing the universe towards its “Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal” State! Indeed, we currently stand at a “historic time”, e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington’s empirical validation of Einstein’s GRT’s “Critical Prediction” of Mercury’s “double-valued” perihelion’s curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT’s & QM’s Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity’s (and Science’s) “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal” State! This is because the very definition of this “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal” State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” – which will also characterize (“guide” and “typify”) Humanity’s newly “Perfected Geulah State”!

Figure 1: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS’ UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

FIGURE 2: The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

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